

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' SCIENTIFIC WORLD VIEW THROUGH PRIMARY CLASS MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS

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Abstract. *This article talks about the formation of students' scientific worldview and their interest in the lesson through the methods used in the classes of mother tongue and reading literacy in primary grades.*

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Today, radical changes are being observed in the field of education in our country. These changes are reflected in pre-school education, primary education, secondary education, as well as higher education. Currently, many changes, researches and scientific works in the field of science are being carried out by experienced research scientists around the world. Including, we can see that radical changes are taking place in the field of education in our country. Mass media and modern methods used in teaching processes are a clear example of this. Effective skills of pedagogues are required especially in order to increase the literacy level of primary school students. Helping elementary school students to write correctly, to improve their speech, and to form their own worldview from the first days of classes is one of the important tasks of a pedagogue. One of the main tasks of elementary school teachers is the formation of students' scientific outlook. In the implementation of this process, the role of education, mathematics, and also mother tongue and reading literacy textbooks is incomparable. A responsible approach by teachers to the tasks given in the mother tongue textbooks is a step towards the result. The exercises in this textbook and the tasks given in the homework section help students to think independently, enrich their scientific worldview, and strengthen their fluency of speech by increasing their vocabulary.

Of course, by using innovative technologies, pedagogues can further increase the knowledge of students, increase their interest in the lesson, expand their worldview, and serve to form their personal thinking. In this regard, the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on February 27, 2020, stated the following in his decision "On measures to further develop the field of pedagogical education»:

"To further improve the field of pedagogic education, to provide professional pedagogic personnel, advanced education to the field, to train highly qualified specialists who have the skills to apply modern knowledge and pedagogical technologies, who will make a worthy contribution to the socio-economic development of our country. introducing technologies..." [1].

It is clear from this that it is important for pedagogues to live with the times and to have deep practical and theoretical knowledge. In the elementary grades, through the mother tongue and reading literacy classes, students are formed the skills of being able to express their personal

opinion independently and become fluent speakers in accordance with all the rules of the language. A. Khalikov's higher education textbook "Pedagogical skills" provides motivational thoughts for teachers about conducting native language and reading literacy classes in primary grades.

Along with skills such as independent thinking, analysis, comparison, interpretation of ideas, argumentation, defense of one's ideas and pursuit of news through creative thinking, in elementary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes, the ability to think logically, worldview, self-awareness, communicative literacy, being mentally and physically healthy, assimilating and appreciating national traditions are developed. This, in turn, ensures that the students of younger age can deeply master their knowledge and apply it correctly in practice. Accordingly, it is important to design the lesson on the basis of pedagogical technology in order to develop students' creative thinking in the primary grade mother tongue and reading literacy classes. The subject of the method of teaching the native language in primary grades is the ways and means of teaching the Uzbek language to students, acquiring the native language, that is, mastering speech, reading and writing, grammar and spelling. Is the science of the methodological basis of the mother tongue teaching methodology is the theory of existence? The main task of this subject is to ensure that students fully master the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. [2]

Various effective methods can be used to form a scientific outlook and further strengthen knowledge in elementary grades.

One of the most effective methods is the problem-based teaching method. The use of the interview method as a problem-based teaching method in primary classes has a great effect on the activation of students in education. The problem-based teaching method was founded by the American pedagogue and psychologist Dune in 1894. The purpose of this method is not only to help mastering scientific concepts, but also to develop students' cognitive abilities and creative abilities. During the conversation, a problem is put before the student by the teacher's task and a problematic situation is created in the lesson. It solves the problem based on the student's previous knowledge. Since elementary school students have little life experience, the teacher asks questions that help solve the problem. If the student cannot solve the problem, the teacher has to solve it. Therefore, the method of problem-based teaching in the primary class is also called the semi-research problem-based method.

It can be added that the method of narration is one of the main methods used in mother tongue classes. In this case, the teacher has determined the students' knowledge of the studied subject before the presentation. This encouraged students to follow and listen to the teacher's explanation and be active. In the teacher's statement, i.e., in the method of presentation, based on the nature of the grammatical topic, the teacher presented the information in his own words. In this case, the teacher is charged with the task of clearly, succinctly and coherently explaining the important points of the studied grammatical topic with the analysis of examples. The presentation method in primary classes is designed for 3-5 minutes, depending on the age and memory of the students. There are still cases of using the method of description. [3]

Many qualities can be formed in students through reading literacy classes in primary grades. For example, in the "conversation method" it is possible to observe the process of respecting each other's opinion and strengthening mutual solidarity. In the course of the lesson, methods are used not only to form a habit in students. It is also used to increase their interest in the lesson and organize leisure time meaningfully. One such effective method used in reading

literacy classes is the "missing information" method. The procedure for using this method is as follows:

Students are divided into small groups. In the handout given to each group, a part of a literary work being studied: a story, a parable or a poem is removed, that is, information is lost. The teacher tells the students that they should find the missing information. Readers begin searching for information related to the information in the book. After reading the work, they find the "missing" information and, based on their knowledge, discuss with the group members and write down the information on paper. Each group restores the missing information. speaks. In this case, the information recovered by the students should preserve the content of the work. [4]

As for the origin of the "Lost Information" method, there is no information about when and by whom this method was created and used. Information about the order in which it will be carried out is given only on the Internet pages. It is no exaggeration to say that many teachers have achieved lesson efficiency by using this method. Because this method ensures an interesting transition of the lesson process and mutual harmony among students.

Another effective method for forming a scientific worldview in primary grades in mother tongue and reading literacy classes is the "SWOT analysis" method. The history of the origin of "SWOT analysis" is described on the web pages as follows:

The acronym SWOT was first coined by Professor Kenneth Andrews at the Harvard Business Policy Conference in 1963. In 1965, four Harvard University professors - Lerner, Christensen, Andrews and Guth - used the SWOT model to develop a company's strategy offered technology. The LCAG scheme (based on the initials of the authors' names) was proposed, which is based on a sequence of steps leading to the choice of a strategy. [5]

This method is not only used in classrooms, but also widely used in economic organizations for working groups. Let's briefly get acquainted with the procedure of its use.

SWOT analysis is a strategic planning method, which consists in determining the factors of the internal and external environment of the organization and dividing them into four categories:

Strong (S) and weak (W) sides are factors of the internal environment of the object being analyzed (that is, what the object itself can affect); Opportunities (O) and threats (T) are environmental factors (that is, those that can affect the object from the outside and are not controlled by the object). For example, the company controls its sales range - this is an internal environmental factor, but the sales laws are not controlled by the company - this is an external environmental factor.

The object of SWOT analysis can be not only an organization, but also other socio-economic objects: economic sectors, cities, state institutions, scientific fields, political parties, non-profit organizations (NPO), individual specialists, individuals. and others.

SWOT analysis also has a number of advantages and disadvantages. The advantage is that it is effective in the initial assessment of the existing situation. The disadvantage is that it cannot replace the development of a topic strategy or a qualitative analysis of the topic. This method can usually be used to analyze the characters of a work, to shed light on their positive and negative characters.

In conclusion, it should be said that the pedagogue has a number of responsibilities for the formation of a scientific worldview in primary classes. That is, he should have theoretical knowledge and skills, be able to attract students to the lesson based on his own experience,

organize the lesson process in an interesting way, and also be able to use modern technologies sufficiently. It is also important for students to be able to use methods based on their interests.

If we look at the introduction of native language and reading literacy textbooks in order to form a scientific worldview in students, one of these textbooks is the vocabulary of our native language, the place of use of words, the use of orthographic and explanatory dictionaries. Moreover, it is a helpful tool for correct pronunciation and correct spelling. When we teach students these concepts from their mother tongue, we further enrich knowledge in reading literacy. In this textbook, students will learn how to use the knowledge they have learned, and will multiply their success by reading poems, stories and fairy tales. If we approach the above-mentioned ideas more clearly, if the teachers teach the topic of methodology in the classes of the mother tongue, they will strengthen the knowledge of the students by how this methodology is applied in reading literacy. Through this, students' thinking expands, and their worldview in the field of science is further formed.

Conducting interesting "ten-minute" exercises for the development of students with low mastery and organizing team games in order to ensure students' harmony has a great impact on the scientific worldview. shows. It can be added that through the interactive methods used in the course of the lesson, the quality of the lesson is improved, mutual cooperation between the teacher and the student, and free creative thinking skills are developed and formed in the students.[6]

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